

and 27° C constant temperature. Length of coleoptile, first leaf, and primary root were measured after 1 week incubation.

Oxygen concentration had little effect on coleoptile emergence, but low O₂ levels enhanced coleoptile elongation. Maximum coleoptile length (20 mm) occurred at 0% O₂. It appears that the rice seed germinated at very low O₂ levels. Root and leaf growth were inhibited at 0% O₂, evidence that low O₂ levels can restrict rice stand establishment.

The critical O₂ concentration for maximum shoot elongation appeared to be about 5%. The critical O₂ concentration for root elongation was less evident. Roots of Labelle and Bellemont seed-

Length of rice leaf, root, and coleoptile after 1 week incubation in water saturated with 10.5% and 1% O₂ at Beaumont, Texas.

Cultivar	Difference (%) in length		
	Leaf	Root	Coleoptile
CB744	-81 ^a	-63	122
IR8	-61 ^a	-60	52
IR24	-78	-77	47 ^a
Labelle	-82	-47	135 ^a
Mars	-68	-78	93
Peta	-64	-63	62
Bellemont	-82	-35 ^a	108
Saturn	-70	-79	74
Starbonnet	-75	-90 ^a	93
TN1	-62	-40	67

^aExtremes for character.

lings reached maximum length at as low as 5% O₂. Roots of Calrose 76 and M 101 seedlings continued to increase in length at 10.5% and 21% O₂.

To help identify cultivars most tolerant of low O₂ concentrations, growth was measured for 10 cultivars in 10.5 and 1% O₂ (see table). When O₂ decreased from 10.5% to 1%, leaf length differences ranged from -61% (IR8) to -81% (CB744). Root length differences ranged from -35% (Bellemont) to -90% (Starbonnet). Coleoptile length differences ranged from 47% (IR24) to 135% (Labelle). Rice cultivars exhibited tolerance for low O₂ levels in one character, but not in the two others. ■

Late planting effects on long-duration semidwarf rices in wetland fields

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Seedling age and time of planting influence rice productivity to a great extent, particularly in short-duration, photoperiod-insensitive cultivars during the rainy season. This experiment examined the effect of late planting on growth duration and yield performance of long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars in wetland fields (20- to 50-cm water depth) during the 1977 rainy season. Materials were 15 long-duration, semidwarf rice cultivars of diverse genetical backgrounds in 2 seedling age groups, 35 days and 60 days old. The experimental design was randomized complete block with four replications. Plots (net) were 4.8 × 2.6 m with plant spacings of 20 × 15 cm and fertilizer applications of 80-40-40 kg NPK/ha.

Grain yields in both normal and late plantings did not differ significantly (see table). However, grain yields of IR32, IR34, CR1006, and IET3257 increased in the late planting. Growth duration increased in all late planted cultivars. Although growth duration increases appreciably, grain yields of normal and late plantings are comparable in long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars. ■

Grain yield and growth duration of long-duration^a semidwarf rice cultivars at normal and late planting dates during 1977 rainy season at Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Cultivar	Grain yield (t/ha)		Growth duration (days)	
	Normal	Late	Normal	Late
IR32	3.4	3.8	149	171
IR34	3.0	3.5	140	163
CR1006	4.0	4.3	158	180
CR1009	4.1	4.0	153	172
ET3257	3.0	3.4	149	160
ET3235	3.3	3.0	140	160
IET4087	3.1	2.7	142	157
IET2991	3.2	2.8	149	153
Pankaj (m) 107	3.8	3.4	147	161
Pankaj (m) 91	3.5	3.0	152	163
HTA448	2.8	2.6	140	167
HTA108	3.5	3.1	149	167
CNBP153-58-2	2.8	2.6	147	159
CNPB134-34-1-1	2.2	2.0	143	161
Pankaj (control)	4.4	4.3	146	164
LSD (0.05) = 0.4 t/ha	0.5	0.6		

^a Maturity of 140 days or more. Normal = 35-day-old seedlings, late = 60-day-old seedlings.

***Sesbania rostrata* green manure and rice**

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To study the effect of *Sesbania rostrata*, a tropical legume that colonizes waterlogged soils in the Senegal Valley, as green manure on rice yield, an experiment was set up in microplots (1 m² each) during the rainy season. Three treatments were used:

Sesbania rostrata green manure. Plots were sown with *S. rostrata* and kept waterlogged for 45 days (stems inoculated by spraying with a culture of *Rhizobium* strain ORS 551). Irrigation

was stopped for 7 days, and the stems of *Sesbania* were cut and plowed in. Nineteen days later, plots were fertilized with PK (17.44 g K₂HPO₄/m²), planted with 2-week-old seedlings of rice cultivar Moroberekan, and waterlogged again.

Mineral nitrogen fertilization. Plots were kept in fallow with the same water management, fertilized with PK and N (23.32 g SO₄ (NH₄)₂/m²), planted, and waterlogged.

Control. Plots were kept in fallow with the same water management, only fertilized with PK, planted, and waterlogged.

Rice was harvested when plants were 135 days old.

In the microplots which had received